

Hard phase crystallization directs the phase segregation of hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymers

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ABSTRACT. A growing body of work shows that the phase behavior of supramolecular polymers assembled from telechelic building blocks featuring binding motifs at the two termini is quite similar to that of conventional block-copolymers. However, it remains unclear how crystallization of the phase formed by the binding motifs, which occurs in many supramolecular polymers, affects the phase morphology of such materials. Here we report a systematic investigation of a series of supramolecular polymers based on poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (PEB) telechelics and the complementary H-bonding pair isophthalic acid – pyridine (IPA-Py). These polymers were designed to feature two blocks that assemble into an amorphous low-glass-transition phase formed by the PEB segments and crystalline domains consisting of the binding motifs. The nature of the latter was systematically varied via the choice of the pyridine employed. The influence of the binding motif on the phase morphology and thereby properties of these supramolecular polymers was investigated by means of thermal analysis, polarized optical microscopy, (dynamic) mechanical analyses, small-angle X-ray scattering, and transmission electron microscopy. In the melted state, all materials assembled into hexagonal phases. However, when cooled below the crystallization temperature of the IPA-Py domains, three different scenarios were observed: breakout crystallization resulting in complex morphologies, retention of the melt morphology, and the formation of a lamellar phase.

INTRODUCTION

Supramolecular polymers (SPs) are macromolecular assemblies of monomeric units that are connected through reversible interactions such as hydrogen bonds, metal-ligand complexes, π - π stacks, or other secondary interactions.¹ SPs are typically accessed via the end-functionalization of telechelic oligomers with supramolecular binding motifs, and the resulting building blocks assemble spontaneously through (self-) complementary interactions into linear or cross-linked structures.²⁻⁵ In the resulting SPs, the supramolecular motifs may phase-segregate from the telechelic core if the polarity difference between them is sufficiently high, and form, in some cases after crystallization, a hard phase.^{3, 5-7} The formation of such hard phase has a strong influence on the mechanical properties as it kinetically traps the dynamic bonds and provides physical cross-links.^{5, 8} The phase segregation behavior of SPs has been compared to the microphase segregation phenomena observed in block-copolymers,⁹ which show a rich variety of long-range ordered microphases, depending on the volume fraction, the degree of polymerization, and the extent of non-miscibility of the blocks.¹⁰ In addition to these parameters, the presence of crystallizable blocks introduces additional complexity to the phase behavior of block-copolymers.¹¹⁻¹² Thus, a semicrystalline diblock copolymer may assemble in different morphologies when cooled from a microphase segregated melt, depending on the nature of the amorphous phase. If the latter is glassy at the crystallization temperature of the crystallizable block, the crystallization is confined and the microstructure will not be disrupted; however, a rubbery amorphous phase may template the crystallization or it may not, in which case the microstructure would be lost in a so-called breakout crystallization.¹¹⁻¹² The microphase morphology of block copolymers can further be tuned with supramolecular interactions,¹³⁻¹⁷ and a few studies have shown that the addition of small hydrogen bonding molecules to block

copolymers with hydrogen bond accepting side groups can have diverse effects including plasticization, confined crystallization and breakout crystallization.¹⁸⁻¹⁹

While the relationship between phase segregation and mechanical properties of SPs is well understood and their assembly into various microphases including lamellar and hexagonal phases has been reported,^{9, 20-24} little is known about the effects of the hard phase's mass fraction and the role of crystallization on their microphase segregation. One reason for this is the predominance of SPs based on self-complementary supramolecular units,¹ which yield single component systems in which the systematic variation of the volume fractions of two different blocks is not trivial. Complementary supramolecular motifs on the other hand are perfectly suited for such purpose if their tendency to self-associate is suppressed by their complementary association constant. Indeed, the synthesis of supramolecular block-copolymer mimics has been achieved by several groups using hetero-complementary binding motifs, including hydrogen bonding pairs and metal-ligand complexes.^{8-9, 25-27} These studies further demonstrated that these supramolecular assemblies organize into microphases, just like block-copolymers, but so far the influence of both the hard phase's mass fraction and its crystallization behavior on the microphase segregation of such systems has not been investigated in detail.

We recently reported a series of SPs based on the isophthalic acid-pyridine (IPA-Py) hetero-complementary hydrogen bonded motif.⁸ Our synthetic approach involved the functionalization of a low-molecular weight telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) with terminal isophthalic acid units and the assembly of the resulting macromonomer with different bipyridines. On account of the IPA's ability to bind with two bipyridines, the resulting supramolecular polymers feature *a priori* network structures, and the large polarity difference leads to phase segregated microstructures in which the IPA-Py motifs form a crystalline hard phase that is separated from

the low-glass-transition-temperature poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) soft phase. It was shown that the melting temperature of the hard phase was affected by the nature of the bipyridine component, and subtle variations in the structure of the latter led to significant changes in the nanostructure of the supramolecular polymer. Taken together, these results suggest that the crystallinity of the IPA-Py phase affects the phase behavior of such SPs and they raise the question to what extent the morphology can be tuned through the bipyridine's structure. Here we address this question through a systematic approach, in which the spacer length and the architecture of the bipyridine were systematically modified, and the corresponding effects on the phase behavior and properties of the SPs were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Dimethyl-5-hydroxyisophthalate (98%, Aldrich), *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (\geq 99%, Fluka), pyridine (extra dry, over molecular sieves 99.5%, Aldrich), potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3) (99%, Aldrich), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (98%, Acros), 4-chloropyridine hydrochloride ($>$ 98%, TCI), 1,4-butanediol (99%, Aldrich), 1,5-pentanediol (\geq 97%, Fluka), 1,6-hexanediol (97%, Aldrich), 1,7-heptanediol (95%, Aldrich), 1,12-dodecanediol (99%, Aldrich), 3-methyl-1,5-pentanediol (\geq 97%, TCI), 1,1,1-tris(hydroxymethyl)propane (\geq 98%, Aldrich), NaH (60% dispersion in mineral oil, Aldrich), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) (extra dry, over molecular sieves, 99.8%, Aldrich), ruthenium(III) chloride hydrate (Aldrich), solution of sodium hypochlorite (13% active chlorine, Acros Organics), $CDCl_3$ (D, 99.8%, Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc.), chlorobenzene- d_5 (C_6D_5Cl) (D, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich), were used as received. Hydroxyl-terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) was kindly donated by Cray Valley Company under the commercial name Krasol HLBH-P 3000 (PEB-OH, number-average molecular weight,

$M_n = 3100 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, functionalization degree 1.9, ethyl branch content 65 mol%), and was used as received. Anhydrous dichloromethane (DCM) was passed through an AlOx solvent purification system before use.

Synthesis of isophthalic acid terminated poly(ethylene-co-butylene) (P1). The three-step synthesis protocol was slightly adapted from a previously reported procedure.⁸

Tosylation of hydroxyl-terminated poly(ethylene-co-butylene). PEB-OH (16.75 g, 5.40 mmol, 1 eq.) and *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (5.15 g, 27.00 mmol, 5 eq.) were placed in a 250 mL round-bottomed flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer, placed under high vacuum for 10 min, and subsequently placed under nitrogen atmosphere. Anhydrous dichloromethane (65 mL) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature until all reagents had completely dissolved. Anhydrous pyridine (2.15 mL, 27.0 mmol, 5 eq.) was subsequently added dropwise via a syringe and the reaction mixture was stirred for 48 h at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. Dichloromethane was then partially removed under reduced pressure until the reaction mixture became turbid and the concentrated dichloromethane solution was precipitated into 500 mL of methanol at room temperature. The precipitate was isolated by decanting the solvent, re-dissolved in a minimum amount of dichloromethane, and precipitated again into 500 mL of methanol at room temperature. The precipitate was re-dissolved and re-precipitated a third time following the same procedure. The product (PEB-TOs) was then dissolved in 300 mL of hexane, washed with 150 mL of brine, and the solution was dried over Na_2SO_4 and directly filtered through a 2.5 cm thick silica pad using hexane as eluent. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford the tosylated product (PEB-TOs) as a transparent slime in 75% yield (14.96 g, 4.04 mmol). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) $\delta = 7.80$ (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 7.34 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}),

5.53-4.64 (m, CH=CH), 4.05 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 2.45 (s, 6H, Ar-CH₃), 2.08-0.55 ppm (m, CH₂ and CH₃ backbone). M_n (¹H NMR end group integration) \approx 3700 g·mol⁻¹.

Synthesis of dimethyl isophthalate terminated poly(ethylene-co-butylene). PEB-TOs (14.75 g, 3.99 mmol, 1 eq.), dimethyl 5-hydroxyisophthalate (4.19 g, 19.93 mmol, 5 eq.) and K₂CO₃ (2.75 g, 19.93 mmol, 5 eq.) were mixed in a 250 mL round-bottomed flask equipped with a magnetic stirrer. A toluene/DMF (1:1, 100 mL/100 mL) mixture was added, the flask was closed with a glass stopper (as a rubber septum did not prevent solvent evaporation) and the reaction mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 24 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and was subsequently filtered through a paper filter to obtain a clear yellow solution. The solvent mixture was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product was precipitated three times in 500 mL of ice-cold methanol from a concentrated THF solution. The product (PEB-MeIPA) was dissolved in 300 mL of hexane, washed with 150 mL of brine, and the solution was dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting product was filtered through a short pad of 2.5 cm of silica using hexane/ethyl acetate 10:1 as eluent. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford PEB-MeIPA as a colorless highly viscous liquid in 75% yield (12.89 g, 3.00 mmol). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 8.26 (s, 2H, CH_{Ar}), 7.74 (s, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 5.37-4.69 (m, CH=CH), 4.05 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 3.94 (s, 12H, -OCH₃), 2.08-0.55 ppm (m, CH₂ and CH₃ backbone). M_n (¹H NMR end group integration) \approx 4300 g·mol⁻¹.

Synthesis of isophthalic acid terminated poly(ethylene-co-butylene) (PI). PEB-MeIPA (6.11 g, 1.42 mmol, 1 eq.) and NaOH (0.45 g, 11.50 mmol, 8 eq.) were dissolved in a mixture of THF/H₂O/EtOH (1:0.1:0.1, 380 mL/38 mL/38 mL) in a 1 L round-bottomed flask. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 5 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. HCl (32%) was dropwise added to the stirred mixture until a pH of 2 was reached and the product had

completely dissolved. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the pH was adjusted again with addition of HCl (32%) dropwise until a pH of 2 was reached. The residue was dissolved in 300 mL of hexane, washed three times with 150 mL of brine and the solution was dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered off. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting sticky solid was precipitated in 700 mL of ice-cold methanol from a concentrated THF solution. The product was dried overnight at 50 °C under high vacuum, affording PEB-IPA (**P1**) as a yellowish slightly turbid solid in 51% yield (4.05 g, 0.72 mmol). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃/TFA) δ = 8.41 (s, 2H, CH_{Ar}), 7.86 (s, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 5.33-4.65 (m, CH=CH), 4.11 (m, 4H, -CH₂-O-), 2.06-0.55 ppm (m, CH₂ and CH₃ backbone). *M_n* (¹H NMR end group integration) ≈ 5600 g·mol⁻¹ (The increase of molecular weight observed is partly due to fractionation during the purification steps).

Synthesis of bipyridines a-g. The procedure was adapted from a previously reported protocol.²⁸ NaH (mineral oil dispersion, 1.00 g, 40.0 mmol, 3 eq.) was placed in a two-necked round-bottomed flask (250 mL) equipped with a magnetic stirrer under nitrogen atmosphere and sealed with septums. The hydride was carefully washed three times with hexane (3 x 7 mL) to remove the mineral oil and the residual solvent was removed under high vacuum. Dry DMF (80 mL) was slowly added while cooling the flask in an ice-water bath and the respective diol (1,4-butandiol, 1,5-pentandiol, 1,6-hexandiol, 1,7-heptandiol, 1,12-dodecandiol, or 3-methyl-1,5-pentandiol, 10.00 mmol, 1 eq.) was added via a syringe. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0 °C, before 4-chloropyridine hydrochloride (2.50 g, 22.00 mmol, 2 eq.) was added and the mixture was stirred for 2 days at 80 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The solvent was distilled off under high vacuum, leaving a paste-like residue, which was triturated with CH₂Cl₂ in a mortar (*important: special care must be taken to avoid breathing CH₂Cl₂ during this procedure, which*

must be performed inside a well-ventilated fumehood) and the mixture was filtered through a filter paper to remove the precipitated salts. This procedure was repeated four times to ensure full product recovery. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield a crude product, which was subjected to column chromatography (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂/MeOH 100:5) to afford the corresponding bipyridine. *1,4-Bis(pyridine-4-yloxy)butane (a)*: Final mass: 0.81 g, yield: 33%, white powder. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 2.01 (m, 4H, CH₂), 4.09 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 6.80 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 8.43 ppm (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}). ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 25.77, 67.33, 110.34, 151.13, 164.97 ppm. MS for C₁₄H₁₆N₂O₂ [M+H] + m/z = 245.1245, found m/z = 245.12822. *T_m* (DSC) = 146 °C. *1,5-Bis(pyridine-4-yloxy)pentane (b)*: Final mass: 1.43 g, yield: 56%, yellowish powder. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 1.67 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.89 (m, 4H, CH₂), 4.04 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 6.80 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 8.42 ppm (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}). ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 22.77, 28.76, 67.66, 110.36, 151.26, 165.07 ppm. MS for C₁₅H₁₈N₂O₂ [M+H] + m/z = 259.1402, found m/z = 259.14433. *T_m* (DSC) = 68 °C. *1,6-Bis(pyridine-4-yloxy)hexane (c)*: Final mass: 1.36 g, yield: 49%, yellowish powder. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 1.55 (m, 4H, CH₂), 1.84 (m, 4H, CH₂), 4.02 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 6.79 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 8.40 ppm (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}). ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 25.88, 28.96, 67.77, 110.38, 151.22, 165.15 ppm. MS for C₁₆H₂₀N₂O₂ [M+H] + m/z = 273.1558, found m/z = 273.15952. *T_m* (DSC) = 131 °C. *1,7-Bis(pyridine-4-yloxy)heptane (d)*: Final mass: 2.09 g, yield: 73%, light yellowish powder. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 1.40 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.51 (m, 4H, CH₂), 1.80 (m, 4H, CH₂), 4.01 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 6.79 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 8.42 ppm (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}). ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 26.02, 28.96, 29.15, 67.88, 110.39, 151.43, 165.17 ppm. MS for C₁₇H₂₂N₂O₂ [M+H] + m/z = 287.1715, found m/z = 287.17510. *T_m* (DSC) = 86 °C. *1,12-Bis(pyridine-4-yloxy)dodecane (e)*: Final mass: 0.72 g, yield: 22%, white powder. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 1.52-1.18 (m, 16 H, CH₂), 1.79 (m, 4H, CH₂), 3.99 (m,

4H, CH₂-O), 6.80 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 8.40 ppm (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}). ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 26.07, 29.03, 29.45, 29.65, 68.02, 110.41, 151.20, 165.22 ppm. MS for C₂₂H₃₂N₂O₂ [M+H] + m/z = 357.2497, found m/z = 357.25393. *T_m* (DSC) = 109 °C. *4,4'-((3-Methylpentane-1,5-diyl)bis(oxy))dipyridine (f)*: Final mass: 0.84 g, yield: 34%, yellow liquid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 1.05 (d, 3H, CH₃), 1.69 (m, 1H, CH), 1.90 (m, 4H, CH₂), 4.08 (m, 4H, CH₂-O), 6.79 (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}), 8.43 ppm (d, 4H, CH_{Ar}). ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ = 19.56, 27.13, 35.86, 65.92, 110.38, 151.20, 165.05 ppm. MS for C₁₆H₂₀N₂O₂ [M+H] + m/z = 273.1558, found m/z = 273.15970. *T_g* (DSC) = -42 °C.

Synthesis of 4,4'-((2-ethyl-2-((pyridine-4-yloxy)methyl)propane-1,3-diyl)bis(oxy))dipyridine (g). NaH (mineral oil dispersion, 1.44 g, 60.00 mmol, 6 eq.) was placed in a two-necked round-bottomed flask (250 mL) equipped with a magnetic stirrer under nitrogen atmosphere and sealed with septums. The salt was carefully washed three times with hexane (10 mL) to remove the mineral oil and the residual solvent was removed under high vacuum. Dry DMF (70 mL) was slowly added while cooling the flask in an ice-water bath and 1,1,1-tris(hydroxymethyl)propane (1.34 g solubilized in 10 mL of dry DMF, 10.00 mmol, 1 eq.) was introduced via a syringe. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0 °C, before 4-chloropyridine hydrochloride (4.5 g, 30.00 mmol, 3 eq.) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2.5 days at 80 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The solvent was distilled off under high vacuum, providing a paste-like residue, which was triturated with CH₂Cl₂ in a mortar (*important: special care must be taken to avoid breathing CH₂Cl₂ during this procedure, which must be performed inside a well-ventilated fumehood*) and filtered through a filter paper to remove the precipitated salts. This procedure was repeated four times to ensure full product recovery. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield the product 4,4'-((2-ethyl-2-((pyridine-4-yloxy)methyl)propane-1,3-

diyl)bis(oxy))dipyridine (**g**) as a yellow powder in 34% yield (1.24 g, 3.40 mmol). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 1.00 (t, 3H, CH_3), 1.83 (q, 2H, CH_2), 4.14 (s, 6H, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 6.83 (d, 6H, CH_{Ar}), 8.42 ppm (d, 6H, CH_{Ar}). ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ = 7.76, 23.14, 42.63, 67.44, 110.35, 151.38, 164.68 ppm. MS for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] + m/z = 366.1773, found m/z = 366.18104. T_m (DSC) = 130 °C.

Supramolecular polymer preparation. PEB-IPA (**P1**, 0.5 g) and a given bipyridine (2.00 mol eq. for **a-f** and 1.33 mol eq. for **g**) were dissolved in 1.5 mL of CDCl_3 . The mixture was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h, at which point the components had fully dissolved. As previously reported,⁸ the $\text{COOH}:\text{Py}$ ratio was monitored by ^1H NMR spectroscopy using the integration of the isophthalic acid signals at 8.41 and 7.88 ppm and the bipyridine signals at 8.48 and 6.78 ppm, and the ratio was adjusted by adding the minority component and re-checking the ^1H NMR integrals until a $\text{COOH}:\text{Py}$ ratio of 1:1 was reached. The solution was then cast onto a glass slide; the solvent was allowed to evaporate at ambient for 48 h in a well-ventilated hood, and the remaining traces of solvent were removed under high vacuum for 2 h at 80 °C. The resulting polymer films (**P1a-P1g**) were removed from the glass slide with the help of a razor blade and stored in a desiccator at room temperature.

Characterization. ^1H -NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 or CDCl_3/TFA as solvent on a Bruker AVANCE III 400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS, but referencing was done on the basis of the CDCl_3 solvent signal (δ = 7.26 ppm), which was used as internal standard. The relaxation time (D1) was set to 5 seconds and the number of scans to 32. Variable-temperature ^1H -NMR spectra of **P1e** were recorded in $\text{C}_6\text{D}_5\text{Cl}$ (10 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) on a Bruker AVANCE III 400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz. Referencing was done on the basis of the $\text{C}_6\text{D}_5\text{Cl}$ solvent signal (δ = 7.14 ppm), which

was used as internal standard. The relaxation time (D1) was set to 5 seconds and the number of scans to 32. Spectra were recorded between 25 °C and 75 °C with an increment of 10°C between measures. ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ as solvent on a Bruker AVANCE III 400 spectrometer operating at 100.63 MHz. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS, but again, referencing was based on the CDCl₃ signal (δ = 77.16 ppm). The relaxation time (D1) was set to 2 seconds and the number of scans to 1024. ESI-MS high resolution mass spectra were measured on an FTMS 4.7T BIOAPEX II. ESI-MS were run on positive mode in acetonitrile. The reported molecular mass (*m/z*) values represent the most abundant monoisotopic mass found. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were performed on a Mettler-Toledo STAR system thermogravimetric analyzer under nitrogen flow between 35 °C and 600 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ using a sample mass of approximately 8 mg. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies were carried out on a Mettler-Toledo STAR system under nitrogen atmosphere, at a heating rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ from -80 °C to 150 or 200 °C using a sample mass of approximately 5 mg. The glass transition temperature *T_g* is reported as the midpoint of the step change in the heat capacity and the melting temperature, *T_m*, was recorded as the minimum of the major endothermic melting peak. Polarized optical microscopy (POM) images were acquired with an Olympus BX51 microscope equipped with a DP72 digital camera and two linear polarizers. Dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA) were conducted on a TA Instruments DMA Q800 equipped with a tension clamp under nitrogen atmosphere. Rectangular samples of the following approximate dimensions: 10 x 5.3 x 0.25 mm, were heated from -10 °C to 150 °C at a heating rate of 3 °C·min⁻¹ while applying an amplitude of 15 μm at a frequency of 1 Hz. Mechanical data are reported as averages of 3 independent measurements. Creep experiments were performed on a TA Instrument DMA Q800 at 25 °C using rectangular samples

of the approximate dimensions 10 x 5.3 x 0.2 mm. The samples were strained to 2% at a strain rate of 5 %·min⁻¹ and the force required to maintain the strain was monitored over time. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements were performed with a NanoMax-IQ camera (Rigaku Innovative Technologies). The camera was equipped with a Cu target sealed tube source (MicroMax 003 microfocus, Rigaku), and the scattering data were recorded by a Pilatus100 K detector (Dectris). The sample-to-detector distance was calibrated using silver behenate. The temperature was controlled *in situ* by a Linkam hot stage HFS-X350-GI heating stage module with a T95 controller. The samples were placed in quartz capillaries (Hilgenberg, Mark-tube made of quartz glass length 80 mm, outside diameter 1.5 mm, wall thickness 0.01 mm) and, when measured at elevated temperature, heated at a rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ to the desired temperature, at which the sample was kept for 10 min before data collection was started. All temperature-dependent SAXS studies were performed by heating the crystallized samples and not by cooling them from the melt, as this would require very long analysis times on account of their slow crystallization. Measurements were performed at several temperatures and raw data were processed according to standard procedures.²⁹ Scattering intensities are presented as function of the momentum transfer $q = 4\pi\lambda^{-1}\cdot\sin(\theta/2)$, where θ is the scattering angle and $\lambda = 0.1524$ nm is the photon wavelength. Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) analyses were performed on a Tecnai Osiris (Thermo Fisher Scientific) at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. STEM images were acquired with a high-angle annular dark-field detector (HAADF-STEM). To enhance the contrast of the features (domains) in the STEM images, the samples were stained by RuO₄. Details on sample preparation can be found in this section.

Crystallization of supramolecular polymers from the melt. In order to maximize the crystallinity of the IPA-Py hard phase, samples of **P1a-P1g** were subjected to multiple

crystallization cycles by melting and subsequent isothermal treatment at different temperatures below their T_m in a DSC. Each sample was heated to 150 °C, cooled to a given crystallization temperature, crystallized at this temperature for 120 min, and cooled to -80 °C, before a heating scan was recorded. This procedure was repeated until the crystallization temperature providing largest melting enthalpy for a single melting peak (thus avoiding or minimizing polymorphism) was identified. The optimal crystallization temperature (T_c) found are **P1a** 42 °C, **P1b** 47 °C, **P1c** and **P1d** 60 °C, **P1e** 38 °C and **P1g** 120 °C, while all attempts to crystallize **P1f** failed (amorphous sample).

Film preparation for DMA and POM analysis. The films of **P1a-P1e** and **P1g** obtained via solvent casting were placed on a glass slide, heated to 20 °C above their respective T_m and immediately placed in an oven that was pre-heated to their respective crystallization temperature (determined as described above) for 12 h. Note that the crystallization time is longer than in the case of the DSC experiments as DSC was only used to find the optimal crystallization temperature and, for time limitations, it would not have been possible to perform multiple 12 h cycles for all samples. The samples were then removed from the oven, allowed to cool to ambient temperature and either used directly for POM analysis or removed from the substrate with the help of a razorblade and cut into rectangular samples of the approximate dimensions 10 mm x 5.3 mm x 0.25 mm for DMA analysis.

SAXS sample preparation. **P1a-P1g** were cut into pieces small enough to fit inside the quartz capillaries (see Procedures section for details). The capillaries were sealed with a commercial epoxy resin (Araldite® Rapid) and the samples were subjected to the crystallization procedure described above, i.e., the samples were heated to 20 °C above their respective T_m and

immediately placed in an oven pre-heated to their respective optimal crystallization temperature for 12 h.

Preparation, cryo-ultramicrotomy and RuO₄ staining of polymer samples for STEM analysis. The films of **P1a-P1g** obtained via solvent casting were compression molded to obtain 100 μm thick films as required for cryo-ultramicrotomy. Thus, **P1a-P1g** were placed between 200 μm thick Teflon[®] sheets and pressed in a Carver CE Press at 10 °C below their respective T_m (and not above T_m to avoid the materials to flow out of the press) using 100 μm thick aluminum foil spacers to control the film thickness. The samples were subjected to 5 tons of pressure for 3 min, removed from the press and placed (still between the Teflon[®] sheets) in an oven that was pre-heated to their respective optimal crystallization temperature (determined as described above) for 12 h. The crystallized films of **P1a-P1g** were cryo-ultramicrotomed at -50 °C with a Leica EM FC7 machine (equipped with a Diatome cryo-knife 35° angle) at a cutting speed of 0.2 mm·s⁻¹, then deposited on an ultra-thin carbon support grid (Electron Microscopy Science CF200-CU-UL). The following procedure must be performed inside a fumehood. The TEM grids were then placed on a Petri dish together with (1 cm distance) a small cup containing the RuO₄ staining mixture, which was freshly prepared by mixing 0.2 g ruthenium trichloride hydrate with 10 mL of 13% active chlorine aqueous sodium hypochlorite.³⁰ The Petri dish was covered with a lid and placed inside a hermetic plastic bag to prevent the vapours of the RuO₄ solution to escape and contaminate the surroundings. The TEM grids were exposed for 30 min at room temperature to the vapours of the RuO₄ solution. Once stained, the samples were stored under vacuum until STEM analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An IPA-functionalized telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) with a number-average molecular weight M_n of 5600 g·mol⁻¹ (**P1**) was used as the first component of the IPA-Py SPs (**Scheme 1**). This macromonomer was synthesized in three steps from the hydroxyl terminated precursor using a slightly modified version of a previously reported procedure⁸ (see Experimental Section). As second component, a series of bipyridines with methylene spacers of varying length (**a-e**), and architecture (**f, g**) were synthesized from the corresponding alcohol derivatives in one step reactions that involved the nucleophilic substitution of 4-chloropyridine in the presence of NaH (**Scheme 1** and Experimental section). While bipyridines **a-e** and **g** are crystalline powders, bipyridine **f** (which has the same spacer length as **b**) is liquid at room temperature, arguably on account of the methyl branch that hampers crystallization. Supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g** were prepared by combining **P1** with the various bipyridines so that the COOH:Py ratio was 1:1;⁸ this was accomplished by dissolving the two components in CHCl₃, adjusting the ratio of **P1** and the respective bipyridine based on ¹H NMR analysis (Experimental Section), solvent casting, and vacuum drying. Note that due to the bifunctional nature of the IPA motif, all polymers made have a network structure (**Scheme 1**). The hydrogen bonded nature of these polymers was confirmed through a variable-temperature NMR experiment with a representative sample. The ¹H NMR of **P1e** was recorded in deuterated chlorobenzene at different temperatures between 25 °C and 75 °C and the signals of the aromatic protons were monitored. As shown in **Supporting Figure S27**, an upfield shift of the signals associated with the protons located in close proximity to the hydrogen bond is observed as the temperature is increased, while the signals associated with the other more distant protons do not shift.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g** based on the combination of IPA-terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) **P1** and the bipyridines **a-g**, and schematic representation of the resulting nanophase segregated assemblies.

The thermal properties of **P1a-P1g** were investigated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, **Figure 1**) experiments. The first heating scan of all solvent-cast samples (**Figure 1a**) shows the glass transition of the poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) backbone at ca. -50 °C as well as (except in the case of **P1f**) several endothermic peaks related to melting of crystalline domains formed by the IPA-Py motifs, indicating that the as-prepared materials adopt phase segregated microstructures, in which polymorphism may also be at play. The samples were therefore crystallized in the DSC with the goal to identify the best crystallization temperature, T_c , for each material. Each sample was heated to 150 °C, cooled to a given crystallization temperature, crystallized at this temperature for 120 min, and cooled to -80 °C, before a heating scan was recorded. This procedure was repeated until the crystallization temperature providing largest melting enthalpy for a single melting peak (thus avoiding or minimizing polymorphism) was

identified. **Figure 1b** shows the first heating scans of all samples after crystallization at T_c , which ranged from 38 °C (**P1e**) to 120 °C (**P1g**, for other values see Caption of **Figure 1**). The traces of **P1a–P1e** all show endothermic transitions between 55 and 78 °C, which are characteristic of the melting of crystalline hard phases, and, in some samples, minor additional endothermic peaks indicative of polymorphism. The melting temperatures, T_m , and the heat flow, which may be taken as a relative approximation of the degree of crystallinity, vary with the bipyridine structure, although there is neither a clear trend nor a correlation with the behavior of the neat bipyridines (**Figure S24**). The DSC trace of **P1f** remains void of any melting transition, and reveals that this material does not crystallize, arguably due to the branched nature of bipyridine **f**. On the other hand, the DSC trace of **P1g** shows that this material crystallizes and displays the highest T_m (130 °C), despite the branched structure of bipyridine **g**. The semicrystalline nature of **P1a–P1e** and **P1g** was corroborated by polarized optical microscopy (POM), which revealed single spherulites for **P1e** after solution casting (**Supporting Figure S28**) and a collapsed spherulites morphology after crystallization from the melt (**Figure 2e**), focal conic textures typical of a hexagonal phase for **P1g** (**Figure 2g**),³¹ and less defined or feature-less birefringence for **P1a–P1d** (**Figure 2a-d**). As expected, the amorphous **P1f** (**Figure 2f**) does not exhibit birefringence. Based on the notion that the physical properties of the materials investigated are related to the crystalline domains formed by the IPA-Py motifs, all further investigations were carried out on samples that had been melt-crystallized for 12 h (time increased with respect to the DSC experiments to maximize crystallization) at their T_c .

Figure 1. DSC traces of supramolecular polymers **P1a–P1g**. a) First heating scans of solution cast samples. b) First heating scans after 2 h of crystallization from the melt in the DSC (crystallization temperature: **P1a**: 42 °C; **P1b**: 47 °C; **P1c** and **P1d**: 60 °C; **P1e**: 38 °C; **P1g**: 120 °C; **P1f**: did not crystallize).

Figure 2. Polarized optical micrographs of films of supramolecular polymers **P1a–P1g** crystallized for 12 h from the melt. a) **P1a** ($T_c = 42\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, scale bar = $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), b) **P1b** ($T_c = 47\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, scale bar = $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), c) **P1c** ($T_c = 60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, scale bar = $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), d) **P1d** ($T_c = 60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, scale bar = $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), e) **P1e** ($T_c = 38\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, scale bar = $20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), f) **P1f** (solvent cast sample, scale bar = $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), **P1g** ($T_c = 120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, scale bar = $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$).

The formation (or absence) of a crystalline hard phase in these supramolecular polymers also affects their mechanical and film-forming properties, as is clearly evidenced by dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA). **Figure 3** shows the DMA traces of **P1a–P1g** which, with the only exception of the amorphous **P1f**, are all characterized by a relatively stable rubbery plateau with storage moduli (E') between 5.2 ± 1.2 and 27.7 ± 2.0 MPa at 25 °C. In addition, a rather sharp modulus drop (leading to eventual mechanical failure) around the T_m of the respective hard phase – which serves as physical cross-link – is observed. In the case of **P1a–d** the modulus drops in multiple steps and mechanical failure occurs at a temperature that is higher than the T_m , which can be ascribed to the presence of minor amounts of higher-melting polymorphs, consistent with the DSC traces (**Figure 1b**). In spite of the fact that **P1f** lacks a crystalline hard phase, this polymer also features a rubbery regime, although the E' is lower than that of the other polymers (4.5 ± 0.5 vs. $6.8 \pm 1.7 - 33.4 \pm 2.4$ MPa at -10 °C) and the modulus decreases gradually above ca. 0 °C, arguably due to the progressive disassembly of the supramolecular motifs – which in this material are not physically trapped by a crystalline phase – upon the temperature increase. **P1e** is by far the stiffest material ($E' = 27.7 \pm 2.0$ MPa at 25 °C), and also has the highest hard phase mass fraction (19 mol%, **Supporting Table S1**) and displays a large melting enthalpy. While it is not possible to directly correlate the stiffness with the hard phase mass fraction and melting enthalpy, the data show clearly that phase separation under formation of glassy and/or crystalline phases that serve as physical cross-links drives a transition from the viscous melts to film forming solid materials. The highest failure temperature is observed for **P1g** (ca. 125 °C), which also displays the highest T_m (130 °C). However, this sample also shows a modulus drop with onset at ca. 60 °C that translates into a clear peak in the corresponding $\tan \delta$ curve (**Supporting Figure S35**). This transition is consistent with the presence of a fraction of non-

crystallized IPA-Py motifs which disassemble as the temperature increases. While such a fraction of non-crystallized motifs is also present in the other samples, the peaks observed in their $\tan \delta$ curves have a lower intensity or overlap with the melting of the hard phase. While the DMA data discussed above show that **P1a–P1g** present reasonably good mechanical properties at room temperature, they remain dynamic materials. To show this, room temperature creep experiments were performed on **P1e** and **P1g** (semicrystalline) and **P1f** (amorphous) as representative samples. The results (**Supporting Figure S36**) show that all three samples creep when subjected to 2% strain independently of their semicrystalline or amorphous nature, albeit a lower force was required to strain **P1f**. The creep tests were complemented with a visual experiment in which a small weight was hang from the same three samples and the creep was visualized during 90 minutes (**Supporting Figure S37**). **P1f** failed after the first minute, **P1g** did not fail but elongated ca. 50% and **P1e** did not creep – in agreement with the previous observation that a higher force was needed to apply a strain of 2%.

Figure 3. DMA traces showing the storage modulus of the supramolecular polymers **P1a–P1g** as a function of temperature (representative curves are shown, the storage moduli provided in the text are average values of three independent measurements).

The morphology of crystallized **P1a–P1g** samples was investigated by room-temperature small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS, **Figure 4a**) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM, **Figure 5** and **Supporting Figures S46–S52**). The scattering patterns and STEM micrographs evidence a strong influence of the bipyridine component on the microstructure. The SAXS patterns of **P1a**, **P1b**, and **P1d** are complex and reveal the presence of several coexisting morphologies (**Figure 4a**), while STEM micrographs show no clearly defined microphase morphologies (**Figure 5**). Indeed, some micrographs of **P1a** (**Supporting Figure S46**) show a hexagonal morphology, which points to a frustrated phase segregation process. The SAXS and

STEM data of **P1c** are in agreement with an ill-defined hexagonal phase, as the ratio of the maxima of the scattering vectors equals $\sqrt{3}$ and $\sqrt{4}$. The SAXS spectrum of **P1e** shows equidistant maxima that are characteristic of a regular lamellar spacing, in accordance with the spherulites observed in the POM images (**Supporting Figure S28**). The SAXS and STEM data of **P1f** and **P1g** indicate distinct hexagonal phases, which in the case of the latter, confirms the POM observations. While **Figure 5g** shows the top view of the hexagonally packed cylinders of **P1g**, additional micrographs of the same sample were acquired that show the cylinders from the top and the side (**Supporting Figure S52**). Interestingly the SAXS spectra of **P1b** and **P1f** reflect very different morphologies, although the bipyridines that used to prepare these polymers only differ by a methyl branching group that is present in **P1f**. Interestingly this polymer – although fully amorphous – shows a very well defined hexagonal pattern. By contrast, the semicrystalline **P1b**, containing a linear bipyridine, displays a complex microphase structure. The STEM micrographs of **P1b** and **P1f** further confirm these observations, i.e., a complex morphology and hexagonal packing, respectively. Taking into account that the mass fraction of the IPA-Py phase is effectively the same in both supramolecular polymers (16.2% for **P1b** and 16.6% for **P1f**), these observations suggest that crystallinity plays a prominent role in the structure formation of these materials. In all cases, the domain spacings extracted from the STEM micrographs (FFT measurements) are in agreement with the scattering data recorded at room temperature (**Supporting Table S2**).

To further explore the effect that the crystallization of the IPA-Py phase has on the microphase morphology of these supramolecular polymers, temperature-dependent SAXS analyses were performed, notably to study their morphology above the T_m of their hard phases. **P1f**, which does

not exhibit a crystalline hard phase, was analyzed at 88 °C, i.e., far above T_g in order to also elucidate a possible influence of temperature on its morphology. **Figure 4b** shows the SAXS spectra of **P1b–P1g** recorded 10 °C above their respective T_m and of **P1a** recorded 50 °C above its T_m (as the pattern change of this last sample became clear only at a higher temperature). The SAXS spectra of all samples at different temperatures are provided as Supporting Information (**Figures S38–S44**). Interestingly, the SAXS patterns of all samples in the melt state show scattering peaks that are indicative of a hexagonal phase, including **P1e**, albeit in this case the structure is less well defined. This suggests that in the absence of any crystallization, the phase behavior is dictated by the mass fraction of the IPA-Py phase, which varied only in a rather narrow range (15.8–19.0% w/w, **Table S1**), and also the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter (χ), which as the results suggest, also appears to be comparable for the polymer series studied. One could speculate that the bipyridines might macro-phase segregate from domains formed by **P1** at high temperatures on account of increasing dissociation of the non-covalent bonds, and be responsible for the formation of the observed hexagonal phase within the poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) phase. To rule out this possibility, we analyzed a sample composed of the parent hydroxyl terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) and bipyridine **b**. As expected, the two components macroscopically de-mixed upon solvent casting from CHCl_3 due to the absence of efficient hydrogen bonding between them. Accordingly, the SAXS spectrum showed no nanoscale phase segregation (**Supporting Figure S45**).

Figure 4. Azimuthally integrated SAXS spectra of supramolecular polymers **P1a–P1g** measured at a) 25 °C and b) 10 °C above the T_m of their hard phase, with the exception of **P1a**, which was measured 50 °C above the T_m of its hard phase. **P1f** does not have a crystalline hard phase and was analyzed at 88 °C, i.e., 140 °C above its T_g . The spectra are shifted vertically for the sake of clarity. The first, second and third order scattering maxima are indicated.

P1f, which is amorphous, shows the same hexagonal scattering morphology in the liquid and the solid state. Also **P1g** displays a hexagonal scattering morphology in both the solid and melted state, which is indicative of a melt phase-templated hard phase crystallization. **P1c** shows an ill-defined hexagonal scattering pattern below the T_m of its hard phase, which becomes better defined when heated above the T_m . On the other hand, **P1a**, **P1b** and **P1d** present complex scattering patterns at room temperature that transform into patterns that clearly reflect hexagonal packing above the T_m of their hard phases. This behavior suggests a breakout crystallization

scenario, in which the crystallization of the hard phase disrupts the ordered melt morphology. Interestingly, **P1e** displays different melt and solid ordered morphologies; lamellar in the solid state and hexagonal in the melt. These results suggest a strong influence of the hard phase's crystallinity on the solid state structure of some of these supramolecular polymers, a behavior that is well-known for block copolymers containing crystalline blocks such as poly(ethylene oxide) or poly(ϵ -caprolactone),³²⁻³⁴ in which the melt nanostructure may be preserved or disrupted upon crystallization. SAXS analyses of all samples were also performed 50 °C above their T_m to investigate the effect of high temperature on their nanostructure. The hexagonal scattering pattern was maintained in all samples; however, a broadening of the signals was observed for **P1d**, **P1f** and **P1g**, indicating a partial loss of order (**Supporting Figures S38-S44**). The temperature was not increased further as the onset of degradation of the bipyridine components **a-g** is between 150 °C and 200 °C (**Supporting Figure S25**). Altogether, the SAXS and STEM data are in good agreement, support the conclusion that the phase behavior of supramolecular polymers **P1a–P1g** is strongly influenced by their crystallinity, and highlight the rich variety of phase morphologies that can be accessed with limited synthetic effort.

Figure 5. Scanning TEM (HAADF detector) micrographs of RuO_4 stained sections of the supramolecular polymers obtained via cryo-ultramicrotoming. The scale bar is 50 nm in all micrographs. a) **P1a**, b) **P1b**, c) **P1c**, d) **P1d**, e) **P1e**, f) **P1f**, g) **P1g**. Samples **P1a–P1e** and **P1g** were crystallized from the melt for 12 h at their respective T_c . **P1f** is amorphous and was analyzed after solvent casting (see Experimental Section for methods). Corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) images are shown as inset with the thereof calculated domain spacings. The width of the FFT image is $500 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in all cases.

CONCLUSIONS

Supramolecular polymers display a phase behavior that is reminiscent of conventional block copolymers. To date, however, their microphase segregation is less well understood and, more specifically, little is known about the effect that the crystallization of one phase has over the phase morphology. In this study, we exploited a modular two-component system in which the composition of a low- T_g amorphous phase was kept constant, while the nature of a crystallizable phase formed by the binding motifs was varied. This approach allowed maintaining the molar fraction and polarity of the two phases virtually identical, and as a result, the formation of similar hexagonal phases of these polymers in their melted state was observed. Interestingly, the materials adopt different solid-state structures, including well-defined hexagonal, lamellar, and mixed phases and the data acquired reveal the crystallization of the binding motifs as a major driver of structure formation. The results show clearly that crystallization plays a very important role on the phase behavior as the supramolecular polymers are cooled from the melt, and different scenarios were observed including breakout crystallization, retention of the melt morphology, and the transition between two well-defined phases. Overall, these results provide new insights into the phase behavior of supramolecular polymers and confirm that, as in the case of block copolymers, a variety of morphologies can be accessed.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Characterization data including ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, and ESI-MS spectra, TGA traces, and additional DSC, DMA, POM, SAXS, and STEM data. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Notes

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Hard phase crystallization directs the phase segregation of hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymers

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